

**METHODOLOGY OF FORMATION OF PHILOSOPHICAL CONCEPTS
IN STUDENT CHEMISTRY**

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PF-4947 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy of further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", dated January 25, 2018 "On measures to radically improve the system of general secondary, secondary special and vocational education" PF-5313, Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 15, 2017 "On measures to introduce new principles of governance in the public education system" Resolution No. 187 of April 6, 2017 "On approval of state educational standards of general secondary and secondary special vocational education", Law of September 24, 2020 No. ZRU-637 "On Education" and August 12, 2020 "On Chemistry and Biology" Resolution No. PQ-4805 "On measures to improve the quality of continuing education and scientific efficiency" The creation of new principles in the implementation of the tasks set out in other normative legal acts in this field is mainly provided by teaching students the basic theories of chemistry in the formation of chemical concepts. 1. Atomic structure theory. 2. Solution theory. 3. Theory of electrolytic dissociation. 4. The theory of the structure of complexes. 5. The theory of the structure of organic chemistry.

The study of each chemical theory, of course, has its own characteristics, but there are many methodological aspects, which apply to all chemical theories. The need itself is one of the general methodological processes. Many textbooks and manuals on chemistry also use two different methodological views on the experience of teaching chemistry to our great Methodist scientists, as well as on how to study theories. The most widely used theory today is the methodology of teaching on the basis of history, but in this method they are limited to teaching historical materials

only in teaching students theories. The second method is based on explaining the theoretical foundations of this modern general chemistry on the basis of scientific materialist dialist theories {3}. At the same time, the explanation of chemical theory is based on the theory by clearly explaining the essence of the theory, giving formulas, proving it on the basis of experiments, as well as focusing on the formation of new chemical concepts in students through the application of teaching methods. Nowadays, in the theory of atomic molecular theory, students begin with molecular assumptions based on concrete facts they have observed. is formed by showing the following experiments from individual physical and chemical phenomena. For example, the teacher demonstrates in a demonstration way the process of burning paper, wood, coal, plastic, justifying the formation of SO₂ and water molecules in substances, the burning substances lose their state. At the same time, students see that as the temperature of a new substance changes, so do their volumes, densities, refractive indices, and changes in boiling and liquefaction temperatures. From there, the Methodist teacher develops a plan for teaching the atomic molecular doctrine. 1. To remove the basic rules of molecular doctrine. To describe the concepts of the atom and the molecule, as well as the element, to say that any substance consists of small particles, to remove the elements N, O, SI, Na, K, Sa, Va, and to form a new substance. can be substantiated. Students are encouraged to observe this experiment by adding water to a container, adding phenophthalene to it, and exposing the purified sodium metal to the water. In this experiment, they observed the formation of sodium hydroxide and gas bubbles in the solution by observing the redness of the solution. leads to the development of the ability and directs the mummy to find a solution.

Students present the mummy solution and state that the redness of the solution is from R_n = 7 on the scale to determine the area of change of the phenophthalin indicator solution because the new substance is alkaline. The Methodist teacher argues that this experiment led to the formation of a new substance by providing additional information on a scientific basis, leading to the formation of a sodium hydroxide base in solution {2}.

Students are based on the basic principles of the theory of the molecular structure of matter, that matter is made up of very small particles - molecules, that there are different increasing and decreasing distances between molecules, and that molecules are in constant motion. The teacher points out that a molecule is a tiny particle that retains the composition and chemical properties of the same substance. At the suggestion of the teacher, the students became aware of all the rules about the molecular structure of substances. They are based on clear facts. The fact that the solids present in matter are composed of fine particles and pores is evidenced by the change in volume when they are heated and cooled, as well as by the compression and expansion of gases when the pressure changes. To prove that molecules are constantly in motion, students recall the diffusion phenomena they are familiar with. In order to further strengthen this phenomenon, the teacher demonstrates in practice the diffusion of a solution of copper sulfate or potassium permanganate, and therefore the diffusion of the odor of odorous substances.

The teacher should summarize all the basic rules of molecular structure of substances and substantiate MV Lomanosov's theory of molecular structure of substances after the students have an understanding of matter. It should be noted that they have proved their existence in nature through scientific theories. By teaching the above theories, students develop philosophical laws about the formation of the laws of nature, the constant movement of nature on the basis of natural confession, the transformation of matter from one species to another.

References.

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